

Comment on "When are AI models ready for deployment? reassessing google's global AI flood forecasting system through the lens of responsible modelling"

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Highlights

- Our metrics align with established humanitarian anticipatory action.
- Li et al.'s suggested metrics fail to capture event discrimination.
- Global models provide crucial data where local forecasts are absent.
- Models must be evaluated for their intended purpose.

Abstract

Li et al. (2026) evaluated our global AI flood forecasting system and critiqued our choice of evaluation metrics and benchmark. Li et al. made the mistake of applying a calibration statistic to measure model discrimination, which is a well-known error in forecast evaluation. The metrics presented in the original paper by Nearing et al. (2024) accurately reflect the ability of the model to predict 1-, 2-, 5-, and 10-year return period events, which are the types of events that trigger anticipatory action under the United Nations' Early Warnings for All initiative.

1. Event Thresholding

Li et al. contend that using modeled climatologies to define event thresholds overstates model accuracy. What they are pointing out is the difference between *calibration* (statistical

consistency of forecasts and observations) and *discrimination* (ability to differentiate observed outcomes or events) in operational forecast verification (Wilks, 2011; Chapter 8).

Anticipatory action relies on predicting event occurrences. The relevant question is: “Will an X-year event occur in this area in the next N days?” Nearing et al.’s metrics are discrimination metrics that measure the ability of a model to discriminate events defined by relative frequency (return period). Li et al.’s metrics are calibration metrics and do *not* accurately measure the ability of a model to predict the occurrence of such events.

We can see this by example. Consider a hypothetically perfect model corrupted by an affine transformation (model error). Even if this transformation is hidden to the user, they still have access to perfect event predictions by simply using event thresholds based on model climatology. Assessing event discrimination with Li et al.’s metrics would not reveal the full and accessible information content of the predictions.

Any type of non-affine model error *does* reduce the accuracy of a model in predicting events, but this type of effect is correctly captured by metrics based on event thresholds from model climatology.

Because of this well-known fact, using event thresholds based on model climatology is standard practice in operational forecast evaluation. Examples include ECMWF’s Extreme Forecast Index (Lalurette, 2003) and GloFAS (Alfieri et al., 2013).

2. Extreme Events

Li et al. assert 10-year return periods “*can hardly be considered extreme,*” arguing for 50- and 100-year event evaluation.

Disaster response organizations generally structure response protocols around lower return periods. The IFRC, which leads the Preparedness & Response pillar of the UN’s Early Warnings for All initiative, uses events with 3- to 10-year return periods (IFRC, 2022). Region-specific Early Action Protocols (EAPs) trigger at a 3-year threshold in Guatemala (IFRC, 2024a); 5-year thresholds in Bangladesh (IFRC, 2024b), Nepal (IFRC, 2024c), Indonesia (IFRC, 2025a), Mali (IFRC, 2025b), Mozambique (IFRC, 2025c), and the Philippines (IFRC, 2021); and 10-year thresholds in Honduras (IFRC, 2023a) and Zambia (IFRC, 2023b). We are not aware of any EAP by a UN agency that uses thresholds larger than 10-years.

Li et al. cite a press release claiming a 20-year threshold used by the IFRC in Zambia. However, this press release states GloFAS *predicted* a 20-year event, not that the trigger requires it. The Zambia EAP document, which is linked in the same press release, specifies a 10-year threshold based on GloFAS.

The public data release with Nearing et al. (2024) includes precision and recall metrics for 20- and 50-year events. These were excluded from the main text during peer review in part due to

the statistical unreliability of estimating rare extremes from short (40-50 year) observational records.

3. Event Windows

Li et al. that a ± 2 -day timing window is inadequate, preferring a strict 0-day tolerance.

Anticipatory action generally consists of several decisions related to prepositioning aid, activating DREF, and communicating warnings. While achieving reliable day-of precision is a worthwhile objective, these decision-based workflows are generally not structured around this type of requirement because it is not necessary in order to take effective action. It is more valuable to know that an event is likely within the next several days if that can be done with higher confidence than predicting the exact date of a flood peak.

We agree with Li et al. that symmetrical event windows lead to potentially missed forecasts at short (i.e., 1- and 2-day) lead times. We recently collaborated to explore the use of asymmetrical event windows for this reason (Alwahshat et al., 2025).

Crucially, however, data released by Nearing et al. (2024) provided precision and recall statistics for 0- and 1-day windows. Our conclusions remain robust: even at 0- and 1-day windows, the AI model provides at least 4 days of extra lead time at statistically similar or better accuracy than GloFAS.

4. Choice of Benchmark

Li et al.'s argument that benchmarking against GloFAS is not sufficient to support operational readiness is inconsistent with the fact that GloFAS has been operational for more than a decade. Both models are operational in the same way: a central organization runs them and supports users through a web interface, APIs, historical data release, and partnerships.

We agree local models are valuable and often superior to global models. However, framing global and locally-calibrated models as mutually exclusive ignores the fact that basic hydrological data is not collected in approximately 40% of countries, and riverine flood forecasting is absent or inadequate in over a third of countries (WMO, 2021).

5. Conclusion

Li et al. claimed that our failure to use their preferred metrics extends beyond a technical disagreement into a question of responsibility and transparency, speculating about a conflict of interest. While such accusations fall outside the bounds of constructive scientific discourse and acceptable professional behavior, it is important to recognize the underlying technical disagreement is related to a failure to adhere to the first principle of model evaluation:

understanding how a model is used (Jakeman et al., 2006).

Declaration of Generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the authors used Gemini to edit, shorten, and improve the readability of the manuscript. After using this tool/service, the authors reviewed and edited the entirety of the text and take full responsibility for the content of the publication.

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